

Đại Bảo Tháp Mandala Tây Thiên (Great Mandala Stupa)

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Đại Bảo Tháp Mandala Tây Thiên is situated inside the Tam Đảo National Park and is part of the larger Tây Thiên spiritual tourism complex, which attracts Hanoians looking for a mountainous spiritual retreat. It houses relics, scriptures and is the central headquarters for Drukpa Vietnam. It is arguably the most widely recognizable Vajrayana temple in Vietnam and Gyalwang Drukpa's visits attract national media coverage. While this entry focuses on Drukpa Vietnam and its main temple, the Great Mandala Stupa, it should be noted that cultural/religious influence is moving both directions between Vietnam and India. For example, Gyalwang Drukpa found out circa 2008 about Vietnamese nuns who practice martial arts. Since then, he has encouraged over 800 nuns across the Himalayas to practice 'kung-fu' and to become chant masters, a role traditionally played only by men. In total, Gyalwang Drukpa has visited Vietnam 12 times. In 2014, he completed a 10-hour service for the departed souls of natural disasters (attended by over 1,000 people). In 2018, he presided over the completion of the massive sand mandala, dedicated to the Bodhisattva Guanyin, which remains housed on the premise. His first visit to Vietnam after the pandemic subsided was in 2023, when he hosted the 3-day Avalokiteshvara Festival at the Great Mandala Stupa, which was live streamed and attended by thousands. One of the main events (besides Gyalwang Drukpa's birthday celebration) was the unfurling of the 12x16 meter Avalokiteshvara Thongdrol ('liberation through seeing') brocade painting, donated in 2017, which is recognized as a world record. The fusion of Vajrayana, spiritual tourism and world records in Vietnam is a feature shared with the 2023 Samten Hills resort.

Date Range: 2011 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Tây Thiên, Vĩnh Phúc province

Region tags: Asia, Southeast Asia, Vietnam

The Great Mandala Stupa is located in Tây Thiên spiritual tourism destination of Đại Đình commune, Tam Đảo district, Vĩnh Phúc province.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Williams-Oerberg, E. (2021). Buddhist Ritual as "Connectionwork": Aesthetics and Technologies of Mediating Religious Belonging, *Numen*, 68(5-6), 488-512. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1163/15685276-12341637>
- Source 2: Drukpa Vietnam. 2015. Đại Bảo Tháp Mandala Tây Thiên [Great Mandala Stupa]. Hanoi: NXB Tôn giáo.
- Source 3: Gyalwang Drukpa. 2012. Everyday Enlightenment: The Essential Guide to Finding Happiness in the Modern World. New York City: Riverhead Books.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8uLXyc_9qzI
- Source 1 Description: A comprehensive video showing the exterior of the temple grounds.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.drukpavietnam.org/>
- Source 2 Description: Official Drukpa Vietnam website
- Source 3 URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hS0rf6XZCVg&t=1s&ab_channel=%C4%90%E1%BA%A1iB%E1%BA%A3oTh%C3%A1pMandalaT%C3%A2yThi%C3%AA
- Source 3 Description: Vietnam National TV coverage on the "Pháp Vũ Rồng Thiên" Photograph Exhibition that celebrates 15 years anniversary of Gyalwang Drukpa coming to Vietnam

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.nytimes.com/2023/02/26/world/asia/nepal-kung-fu-nuns.html>
- Source 1 Description: Gyalwang Drukpa's group of nuns trained in martial arts
- Source 2 URL: <https://e.vnexpress.net/news/life/monks-put-finishing-touches-to-vietnam-s-largest-jeweled-mandala-ahead-of-grand-unveiling-3723022.html>
- Source 2 Description: The largest jeweled sand mandala at Great Mandala Stupa
- Source 3 URL: <https://mattersindia.com/2017/03/buddhist-leader-presents-giant-sized-painting-to-vietnam>
- Source 3 Description: The world's largest religious painting housed at Great Mandala Stupa

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

DRAFT
– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Mountain

Notes: Tây Thiên is located on the slopes of Thạch Bàn mountain, Tam Đảo range. The area is known for long-standing Buddhist history that flourished during the Trần Dynasty (1225-1400). Now, it is a famous spiritual tourist destination.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Clearing

– Trackway or road-surface

– Water feature

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: Tây Thiên is located in a mountainous commune of Đại Đình, north of Tam Đảo district, with less than 10,000 residents.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Notes: The temple complex is 10 hectares large and is about 45 kilometers away from Hanoi.

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Tây Thiên is a prominent spiritual tourism destination in Vĩnh Phúc province with convenient routes of travel for large tour buses.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: Tây Thiên is historically known as spiritual land of Buddhism and Đạo Mẫu (Mother Goddess Religion). In 1991, Tây Thiên was recognized as a national historical site.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Notes: Construction began in 2011 and the first abbot was Thích nữ Minh Giác. The design is based on cosmic architecture of the mandala and includes the Dharma Realm and directional Bodhisattvas. It has a diameter of 60 meters at its base, is 37 meters high and is situated in the middle of a manmade lake.

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: Several features including stupas, kora, statues, and buildings.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: The location where the stupa is built was hand-picked by Gyalwang Drukpa. The design is inspired by the mandala symbolizing the universe. The main stupa and several structures was constructed in 2011. The construction continues on until present day and during our field visit in February 2023, a few small structures are still being built.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: The architectural design of the Great Mandala Stupa depicts the mandala with the base, dome and yasti represent the Body-Speech-Mind of the Buddha. The stupa is surrounded by an artificial lake symbolizes wisdom and great bliss.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The Great Mandala Stupa is part of Tây Thiên spiritual landscape with the presence of Mahayana Buddhism and Đạo Mẫu (Mother Goddess Religion).

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Notes: It is the site of many empowerments, especially during the Lunar New Year celebrations, with the visit of Gyalwang Drukpa and his sangha, that attract thousands of people. Other times during the year, there are monthly circumambulation ceremonies dedicated to specific Tibetan Buddhism deities.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– No

Notes: Even though the construction of main stupa has been finished, that of other minor structures (stupas, praying wheel) is still going on.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Notes: A panoply of Tibetan Buddhist deities.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The commission behind the construction of the Great Mandala Stupa is unclear, however, the Drukpa lineage in Vietnam is famous for having followers with excessive wealth and political power. Some might have maneuvered and influenced the political system in order to facilitate the establishment of Drukpa lineage and the construction of the temple.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

–Other [specify]: Gyalwang Drukpa came to the piece of land of hand-picked the exact location for the main stupa, as well as the design and purification.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The financial resources contributing to the construction of the Great Mandala Stupa is unclear, however, the Drukpa lineage in Vietnam is famous for having followers with excessive wealth and political power. Some might have donated to the construction and operation of the temple.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Notes: The Great Mandala Stupa is proudly promoted as the center of the universe, according to the mandala, where quintessential energy of heaven and earth converge and spread to other parts of the country.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: There are sacred texts housed at the Great Mandala Stupa, but it was not constructed specifically and solely for this purpose.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The complex consists of multiple spiritual structures besides the main stupa that is located in the middle of an artificial lake, namely the bell tower, Guru Rinpoche Mandala, Mandala Zhitro, and Namgyelma stupa.

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The main stupa is of greatest significance within the complex.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– I don't know

Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 37

Notes: Width at base.

Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 60

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:
– I don't know
Notes: Structures have varied sizes.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type
– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Cement, bronze

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

Notes: Vajrayana iconography is a vital aspect of the Great Mandala Stupa.

↳ On the outside:
– Yes

↳ On the inside:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
– Yes

Notes: Thangkas are movable and many statues and objects are movable and can migrate from inside the stupa to the outside rings of the kora. Once a year there is a festival for the unfurling of the 12x16 meter Avalokiteshvara Thongdrol.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:
– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:
– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:
– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

- Yes
- ↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:
 - No
- ↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it geometric/abstract
 - Yes
 - ↳ Floral motifs
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it writing/caligraphy
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: NA
- ↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can the decoration be revealed:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there statues present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Cult statues:
 - No
 - ↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Statues of humans:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: Around the kora are cardboard-printed statues of various Tibetan Buddhism deities.
- ↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

 - No
- ↳ Are there paintings present:
 - Yes
 - Notes: There are ceiling paintings and thangkas, but the majority of wall area inside the main

stupa is covered with low-quality printed decal wallpaper of Tibetan decorations.

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:
– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:
– Yes

↳ Type
– 'True' fresco
– Other [specify]: Printed decal wallpaper

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:
– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:
– Yes
Notes: Life of the Buddha is carved and painted on the ceiling.

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:
– No

↳ Other [Specify]
– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there mosaics present:
– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
– No

↳ Other type of decoration:
– Yes [specify]: Buddhist flag and lungta

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Notes: The iconography is done according to specifications as seen in Tibetan cultural areas. It is not distinct although the inclusion of Sino-Vietnamese aesthetics styles (i.e. depiction dragon circling the columns inside the main stupa) is somewhat new and a growing trend in Vietnam.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: Tibetan Buddhism does not have a singular supreme god -- but rather a vast array of deities with different ritual and spiritual roles.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: However, many deities are represented in various statues and iconographies and are in communication with followers.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

Notes: In the Drukpa lineage, Tulkus are reincarnated lamas and are technically human-divine beings (although not exactly thought of as such in emic language of followers).

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Of course, the primary Tulku of Great Mandala Stupa is Jigme Pema Wangchen, the current lineage holder, who was born in India in 1963. He is a tulku in the line of reincarnate masters going back to the first Gyalwang Drukpa, the founder. Followers of Drukpa, both Vietnamese and Tibeans, can experience forms of communication with Gyalwang Drukpa, both in person and through spiritual practices.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Notes: There is a painting of Gyalwang Drukpa on a raised alter, but no cult statues.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

Notes: Nuns at Great Mandala Stupa are under specific vows that mandate regulations and are enforced socially and through supernatural monitoring.

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

– Yes [specify]: during rituals

↳ Offerings of food:

– Yes [specify]: during rituals (tsok)

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– No

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– No

↳ Daily life objects:

– No

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: Incest taboo is operative. Sexual norms are regulated for nuns and among laity is not stressed. Buddhist nuns are generally regulated by the monastic code (bhikṣunī prātimokṣa) and sexual norms follow Vinaya precepts.

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:
– Yes

↳ Other:
– Other [specify]: N/A

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Communication happens through personal prayer and the performance of public rituals that are hosted at Great Mandala Stupa. Children are also socialized into circumambulating and other ritual practices -- <https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=615748740472838&ref=sharing>

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:
– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:
– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
– specify: From an individual person to thousands of people.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: Regularly, but especially concentrated around visits of Gyalwang Drukpa and his team from India.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: The Great Mandala Stupa and Gyalwang Drukpa have less synchronic practices than other lineages (specifically Sakya Vietnam, which has hybrid features with Đạo Mẫu). However, Vietnamese followers are likely to have synchronic practices -- especially around ancestor worship.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: Besides financial donations, small objects and foodstuff are given.

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: Construction has happened in stages and is ongoing.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
– Yes

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: People often describe getting to Great Mandala Stupa and doing kora there as a kind of pilgrimage. In Tibetan Buddhism, practitioners make circumambulation around a sacred site as a type of pilgrimage and meditative practice. Circumambulation rituals for rotating deities are often hosted at Great Mandala Stupa, and people attend with the mentality of pilgrimage (to travel long distances, and walk long distances, with a group of like-minded people executing a specific goal like 108 circumambulations).

<https://www.facebook.com/daibaothap.mandala.taythien/posts/pfbid08M33QyYbaWAGjQiamRpnpdFV5b7Aymp5f24PPYY5LguBqk>

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:
– No

Notes: Not in a strict sense, but because Great Mandala Stupa is in a temple complex in the mountains somewhat far away from Hanoi, casual visitors and ardent followers who go there are doing a form of either pilgrimage or short-term spiritual tourism.

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
– Yes

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:
– Yes

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:
– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:
– Yes

↳ Priests
– Yes

↳ Local elites
– Yes

↳ Private contributions
– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Contributions will come from leadership, patrons and private contributions from followers.

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: communal area

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Routinely and based around the schedule of Gyalwang Drukpa

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

↳ Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:

– Yes

↳ Requires new construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

↳ Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Depends on the event. Some festivals have several thousands in attendance.
<https://e.vnexpress.net/photo/news/gyalwang-drukpa-leads-peace-festival-at-vinh-phuc-stupa-4564208.html>.

Notes: Another popular festival for the larger complex at Tây Thiên is the Spring Festival organised from the 15th-17th of the second lunar month each year to commemorate Quốc Mẫu Tây Thiên, the mother goddess worshiped at the complex.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Religious professionals

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– I don't know

Notes: It is unclear how frequent divination practices are done at Great Mandala Stupa. Certainly, individuals can receive forms of healing through Great Mandala Stupa -- we have recorded individual laity and nuns who have been healed of various psycho-biological problems. Divination, if it occurs, is a private practice between a follower (who makes a donation) and a specific Tibetan monastic (when in residence). There are also some Vietnamese women who may do informal and localized divination

practices somewhat unrelated to Tibetan Buddhism (or loosely connected to it).

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– Yes

↳ Cleansing

– No

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: The sangha at the stupa consists of 200 monks and nuns. Some of them can speak Tibetan fluently and act as translators whenever the Drukpa sangha comes to the stupa.

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Notes: All the nuns live inside the residential area within the Tây Thiên complex.

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Notes: Gyalwang Drukpa and his sangha pay annual visit to Great Mandala Stupa around Tết Nguyên đán (Vietnamese Lunar New Year) for religious ceremonies. Gyalwang Drukpa is the reincarnate spiritual leader of the Drukpa lineage, founded by Naropa over 1,000 years ago. He first visited Vietnam in 2007. He is a passionate environmentalist and protector of the Himalayas, where he is the founder of the Druk White Lotus School in Ladakh and the Druk Gawa Khilwa Nunnery in Kathmandu, which promotes female education. His 'Live to Love' consortium of NPOs, founded in 2007, promotes environmentalism, gender equality and cultural heritage preservation. He is a mountain ambassador and has organized a Guinness record for most trees planted between 2010-12.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Great Mandala Stupa is a nunnery headed by Thích nữ Minh Giác. She is the student of the famous Thích Minh Tịnh, who is prominent Vajrayana monk in Vietnam.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
– Field doesn't know
Notes: It is common for nuns to live in a temple for life. However, they might receive reallocation order to serve as abbots of other temples in the future.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:
– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:
– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:
– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:
Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders
– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:
A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.
– Field doesn't know
Notes: Great Mandala Stupa is under the administrative monitoring of the Vietnam Buddhist Sangha (VBS), as any other officially recognized Buddhist sites are in Vietnam. It is also located within the spiritual destination of Tây Thiên at Tam Đảo, it might also be under the monitoring and supervision of the local Department of Culture, Sports and Tourism.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):
– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:
– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out land:
– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:
– No

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Notes: Even though the Great Mandala Stupa is not an official location of community services, there are events hosted at the stupa for charity (food distribution) and spiritual (blessings for the deceased) purposes.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: Not scriptures, but the entire complex of Tây Thiên (of which Great Mandala Stupa is a part) is dedicated to fairy Lăng Thị Tiêu -- one of the seven fairies Jade Emperor who specializes in the treatment of diseases.